

THE DECENTRALIZED AND AUTOMATED ECONOMY

A RESEARCH ROADMAP
FOR THE MEDIUM-TERM
FUTURE

CREATe Working Paper 2025/3

KONSTANTINOS STYLIANOU
ZIHAO LI

CREATe

The Decentralized and Automated Economy: A research roadmap for the medium-term future

Konstantinos Stylianou and Zihao Li*

Abstract

This working paper sets a research agenda for the decentralized and automated economy drawing on a roundtable event organized by CREATE. The event gathered diverse stakeholders to identify key open issues that are likely to become pressing and crucial in regulating and navigating markets based on AI and decentralized technologies. Topics include trust and governance in decentralized finance (DeFi), the rise of private money (e.g., stablecoins), regulatory fragmentation, AI governance, and manipulative AI-driven design (dark patterns). The insights offered herein reflect a synthesis of stakeholders' collective contributions, which represent different interests, industries, and backgrounds.

* Konstantinos Stylianou is Professor of Competition Law and Regulation and Zihao Li is Lecturer in Law and Technology, both at CREATE, School of Law, University of Glasgow.

On 18 October 2024, CREATE held the launch event of the new research theme 'Decentralization, Automation, Platforms'. The deployment and wide adoption of technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and AI have transformed modern economies so rapidly that law and policy have barely had enough time to adapt. New domains of economic activity such as decentralized finance and generative AI are opening up, and despite heightened regulatory and academic interest in these areas, there is still a sense of lack of coherent direction in terms of safeguards, regulation, and policy-making more broadly.

In this context, we brought together a diverse stakeholder group to weigh in on the high-level challenges the decentralized and automated economy faces. There has been no shortage of challenges, worries, sources of concern, but also aspirations, excitement, and hopes (whether validated or dashed) in these areas. From the exposure of users to the extreme volatility and opportunism of crypto markets, to issues of international cooperation in devising effective regulation, to fears around the expanding dominance of BigTech in AI, and to the weaponization of AI and crypto hacks for political purposes, the decentralized and automated economy is teeming with novel questions, and indeed many of them having emerged only very recently.

Our goal was not to dictate an agenda or suggest priorities; this was a **semi-structured roundtable** operating under Chatham House rules, where stakeholders had an opportunity to **freely explore issues** and questions without being bound by a fixed agenda. This way, and in the space of a full day, we could identify themes that stakeholders considered more pressing, under-explored, or simply interesting. This was not meant as a comprehensive exercise, but it does reflect a certain measure of imperativeness around the areas identified, which CREATE intends to be active in and invites collaboration on, and which we are sharing with the world to inform agenda-setting, prioritization, and research exploration.

The following **institutions were represented** (alphabetically):

- Algorand (financial industry)
- Bank for International Settlements (international organization, banking)
- Digital Euro (advocacy)
- EU Parliament (government)
- Free University Amsterdam (academia)
- Gunnercooke (legal practice)
- KPMG (consulting)
- Scottish government (government)
- Tiktok (ByteDance) (software industry)

- Tongji University (academia)
- Travers Smith (legal practice)
- University of Amsterdam (academia)
- University of Glasgow (academia)

Through the roundtable, a number of **themes, issues, and questions arose**. They represent stakeholders' concerns and ideas about where the decentralized and automated economy is headed, where it may stumble, and what conflicts may arise along the way. An exploratory exercise at its heart, the goal was to highlight areas we have been oblivious to, we should be paying attention to, prioritize, or reassess their significance. We do not purport to offer answers; at best, the roundtable insights provide initial guidance. The issues identified below are meant to **drive research agendas, inform priority-setting, limit blind spots, and incite new discussions**.

As our work in this area continues, we invite readers to reflect on these issues, share thoughts or objections with us, or reach out with project proposals and forward thinking ideas.

1. Decentralized economy

A great deal has already been written about the decentralized economy and its main technological underpinning, the Distributed Ledger Technology. Its supporters extol its potential for a new economic order where wealth and power is distributed and access to capital is democratized; its critics deride the lack of real world uses, its increasing capture by incumbent interests, and the underwhelming deliverables. The truth lies somewhere in the middle: even though the decentralized economy may have failed to live up to its initial lofty aspirations, it has captured the attention and active involvement of every major stakeholder group, including governments, central banks, financial incumbents and financial startups, international organizations, regulatory authorities, and individual users, developers, and infrastructure providers.

1.1. Trust and governance

While blockchain is known as a trustless technology, trust has become a major determinant of Decentralized Finance's (DeFi) uptake and success. The question is trust in what or whom.

Blockchain was born out of a desire to bypass trusted intermediaries. In lieu of intermediaries, blockchain relocated trust in the technology itself. Parties transact not because they know and

trust each other, nor because they trust the intermediaries between them, but because they trust that the blockchain network itself is built to eliminate malicious acts.

However, the decentralized economy, and particularly Decentralized Finance (DeFi) have pivoted back to trusted intermediaries as they integrate with mainstream economy. Crypto-exchanges, custodians, application and service developers, and even traditional financial institutions and instruments are now the new trusted intermediaries that drive DeFi's adoption. And while (some of) those intermediaries are new compared to the old economy, they are still intermediaries, and they come with the usual pros and cons of intermediaries: they speed up uptake of new products and services and they facilitate people's interactions and transactions, but they also serve as central points of failure and control.

As the 're-intermediation' of the decentralized economy is underway a familiar question emerges: where do people place their trust in this new system? Is it the government, traditional private actors such as commercial banks, new private actors such as a DeFi institution, or is it simply the technology itself, like blockchain, assuming people still recognize and rely on its trustless nature? Trust is key, because without it, people are unlikely to use a system.

So far, no clear direction is emerging. The rise of crypto offerings through the conventional financial system (e.g. Bitcoin ETF), the growing centralization of key DeFi functions, chiefly in exchange and custodian markets, the distrust of the public toward Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs), and the enduring appeal and use of new-world DeFi and other applications of DLT are all evidence of people's preferences, but they point to different directions; some support the incumbent system, some remain subversive.

What complicates the picture even further is that the actors, products, and services of the decentralized economy do not have static governance structures. Governance regulates how a system functions and who and under which circumstances has power and control within and over the system. Because governance in the decentralized economy has historically relied on informal decentralized social production, it is ever-shifting and unpredictable compared to the more formal and solidified structures of traditional firm-based production models. This protean nature of governance creates a constant shift in trust and user expectations making it harder to pinpoint points of control and failure.

1.2. Fragmentation of money

New forms of private money—often competing—are emerging creating tension between people's desire for freedom and their desire for stability and trust in the financial system.

General purpose private money, such as stablecoins, are increasingly being used as substitutes for fiat money. These are flexible and easy to use, but largely unregulated. Users are torn between different regulatory priorities. On the one hand, they expect the government to oversee issuers to ensure the safety, stability, and efficiency of the financial system. On the other hand, they distrust the government, especially as regards privacy and control over their finances and transactions.

Moreover, governments, through Central Banks, grapple with the macroeconomic effects of alternative forms of money. Digital denominations of sovereign money (such as USDT) are currently beyond the control of Central Banks, and yet they can interfere with monetary policy and reduce sovereignty. This is not only because they are pegged to fiat money, but also because they blend features that have so far been distinct (e.g. stablecoins that pay interest funded by investments, which blends cash and securities). While the transaction volume of alternative forms of money is currently minuscule, this is an area of growing concern.

There is also a sense that the regulatory subjects are a moving target. Because alternative forms of money are new, rapidly changing, and issued by diverse actors (including decentralized actors which are harder to pinpoint), it is difficult for regulators to know which actors and which activities to prioritize. Moreover, crypto-economy offerings are characterized by fads (e.g. memecoins, NFTs); when these raise regulatory concerns, it may be wasteful to develop regulatory responses only for the relevant products and services to disappear from the market shortly thereafter.

One way to counter fragmentation and wastefulness is for governments to develop—and then proceed to regulate—the desired infrastructure, which will supplant market offerings. For example, the Bank for International Settlements is leading efforts to develop cross-border payment systems between Central Banks and/or commercial banks that compete with blockchain offerings such as Ripple. If successful, such offerings can steer the market in government-sanctioned directions. If existing established technologies and solutions are to be replaced by a DLT solution, they need to make sure that they can at least have the same key benefits. The replacement of a global financial system like SWIFT will need at the very least be as extensive, cheap, interoperable, secure, low cost etc, and fragmented national solutions or business solutions that do not meet the global scale necessary may be of limited use. Perhaps that explains the slower than anticipated adoption of DLT solutions in what is likely paradigmatic case studies such as cross-border transactions.

1.3. DLT as a FOMO technology and the role of interoperability

While it is up to the market to determine the value and utility of DLT products and services, there is a lingering sense that what is driving some involvement is fear of missing out on the opportunities presented by the crypto-economy. On the other hand, interoperability and the general-purpose nature of DLT can be a major driving force.

There is still skepticism around the value of products and services based on distributed ledgers. For some much-hyped DLT applications such as wholesale CBDCs there already exist non-DLT equivalents in actual operation. In other situations where it is well recognized that the technology underpinning the global financial system is inefficient, it is not clear that DLT is the answer. For example, Ripple's cross-border transaction network is promising, but one does not need DLT for cost-effective, instantaneous, secure cross-border transactions. Current inefficiencies stem from path-dependency symptoms of how the financial system developed over the years, not because available technologies (beyond DLT) do not exist to improve the system. Therefore, if it is to be overhauled, DLT is but one of the available technologies. It is telling that few 'killer apps' in the DLT space exist—mainly stablecoins—even though the technology has been around for 15 years.

Interoperability seems to be a key driver of DLT's promise. Because DLT is general purpose, any DLT application can be designed to work with other DLT applications, and even when this is not the case, interoperability solutions like bridges, which can fill the gap of by-design interoperability, exist. This exponentially increases the utility of each application. While taken individually, non-DLT applications could offer similar functionality to that of a given DLT application, they would still lack the breath of the DLT general purpose nature. For example, a cross-border transaction network based on DLT can then easily be integrated with smart contracts, even if the original design did not include that functionality from the outside. Therefore, even if taken in isolation DLT-based products and services may not be superior to existing (non-DLT) solutions, the unbounded generative nature of DLT and the ensuing interoperability among DLT products and services makes DLT a compelling future-proof solution.

1.4. Tax design

Corporations in particular may be reluctant to explore cryptoassets until they understand their tax treatment. Governments can use taxation as a means of (dis)incentives.

Experts and authorities need to figure out the tax implications of cryptoassets, especially in terms of disposing them and gaining rewards from staking them. While individuals may be willing to take a more lax approach to compliance, corporations will find it harder to endorse cryptoassets if they do not fully understand and are in the position to assess their tax treatment. Clarity in this area is key, but so is stability. Some tax authorities, like the UK and the US, have released guidance on the tax treatment of cryptoassets, which focuses on when cryptoasset disposal can be taxed and which cryptoasset activities need to be taxed.

The taxation of crypto assets is also linked to their adoption through the establishment of taxation incentives or disincentives. For example, while Portugal and Germany chose to not tax the sale of cryptoassets, India applies a flat 30% tax, which can be disincentivizing. Governments can use taxation to influence both the degree of activity around cryptoassets, but also how they are perceived by the public. For instance, if cryptoassets are taxed at the same higher rate as gambling profits, this may signal to the market that the government sees cryptoassets as similar to gambling activities, even though it may not have explicitly taken that position.

1.5. Regulation and enforcement depend on priority setting

Regulatory authorities and enforcers necessarily prioritize which rulemaking or enforcement activities they can afford to pursue. In an industry where headline-grabbing illicit activity abounds, regulators may need to effectively communicate their rationale for action or inaction, since enforcement and rulemaking in the decentralized economy may differ from traditional financial markets.

It is no secret that regulatory authorities have limited resources. This affects their decisions both in terms of rulemaking and in terms of enforcement. The norm is that they prioritize issues on the basis of likelihood of harm and severity of harm. There has been intense regulatory activity around cryptos indicating that regulators are concerned about widespread harm to consumers from the use of cryptos. Contrast that with AI, which, even though it has attracted immense attention, including regarding apocalyptic socio-economic consequences, regulatory initiatives have remained limited and enforcement muted.

Despite the intense regulatory scrutiny of cryptoassets, the degree to which regulatory resources should be committed to rulemaking in the decentralized economy remains unclear. As mentioned earlier, for some stakeholders (and for a part of the public) trust remains paramount, and therefore they are willing to see resources allocated in ensuring the decentralized economy is an area of trusted transactions. The same stakeholders, however, may not necessarily

consider the decentralized economy a big enough space to warrant the commitment of elevated resources. Yet for other stakeholders, the benefits of innovation and financial prospects the decentralized economy promises are sufficient to justify a laxer approach.

In terms of policing the decentralized economy, added complexity emerges. The global decentralized nature of cryptoassets makes enforcement less effective. Seizing assets, regulating actors, tracing transactions, gathering evidence, executing legal instruments, and generally enforcing the law are all limited by the global decentralized modus operandi of cryptoassets, and enforcers need to decide whether the additional resources needed to coordinate with foreign counterparts, if that is even possible, are good value for money. While people often lament the occurrence of illicit activities in the crypto space, they would not necessarily want enforcers to commit disproportionate resources to rectifying or preventing such activity.

Obviously, each jurisdiction and each regulator can decide for themselves how to prioritize their enforcement activities. Whatever their decision, however, it may be a good idea to be able to communicate to the public and to other branches of the government why and how they pursue certain enforcement activities over others. This can help their legitimacy.

2. Automated Economy

While blockchain and AI are fundamentally different technologies, the workshop discussions revealed a number of parallel challenges—from hype-driven investment and fragmented regulation to difficulties ensuring transparency and accountability. These experiences with blockchain regulation offer lessons that can inform AI governance. As we turn to the subject of AI, we can draw upon the regulatory insights gained from earlier technology cycles—particularly around the need for robust legal frameworks, clear definitions of authority, and safeguards against monopolization or misuse. By examining these parallels and their implications for AI, we lay the groundwork for identifying practical research and policy directions in the evolving landscape of artificial intelligence.

2.1. AI and constitutional challenges

The deployment of AI systems, particularly in public decision-making, challenges foundational constitutional and legal principles, raising critical questions about the lawful authority of the state, the transparency of algorithmic governance, and the need for a settled legal framework to regulate AI without undermining constitutional norms.

The integration of AI into public decision-making processes, such as policing and welfare, has exposed significant gaps in existing legal and constitutional frameworks. These technologies challenge traditional assumptions about lawful authority, transparency, and accountability, necessitating a re-evaluation of how legal systems adapt to the unique complexities of AI. At the heart of this challenge is the question of what authority the state has to deploy AI systems and how such authority is exercised in a manner consistent with constitutional principles.

Under the social contract, the state derives its power from the public to act in their interest, prevent harm, and uphold the rule of law. However, AI systems complicate this relationship by introducing new forms of decision-making that operate beyond the scope of traditional legal frameworks. For instance, in the UK, the use of AI in policing is grounded in common law principles that grant police the authority to protect the public and investigate crimes. Yet, these principles do not explicitly address the use of automated decision-making tools, leaving a legal vacuum that raises constitutional, administrative, and human rights concerns. This lack of clarity undermines the legitimacy of AI-driven decisions and challenges the very foundations of lawful authority.

A key issue is the absence of a clear legal basis for the use of AI in public decision-making. In the UK, for example, there is no specific statutory framework governing the use of automated decision-making systems, apart from limited interpretations of the Data Protection Act. This creates a situation where decision-makers must derive their authority from fragmented and often outdated legal sources, leading to potential conflicts with constitutional norms. The deployment of predictive analytics in policing, for instance, raises questions about the limits of state power and the protection of individual rights. Without a settled legal framework, the use of such systems risks eroding public trust and undermining the rule of law.

Transparency and accountability are further complicated by the opacity of AI systems. In the UK, police authorities often lack comprehensive records of the AI tools they use, including details about the data they collect and the algorithms they employ. This lack of transparency not only hinders public oversight but also makes it difficult to assess the legality and fairness of AI-driven decisions. For example, according to one of the panelists, a Freedom of Information request revealed that some police forces could not quantify how they were using predictive analytics or what data they were collecting. This opacity is not merely a technical issue but a constitutional one, as it undermines the principles of accountability and due process that are central to democratic governance.

The human rights implications of AI further underscore the need for a robust legal framework. AI systems, particularly those used in sensitive areas like policing and welfare, have the potential to infringe on fundamental rights, including privacy, non-discrimination, and due process. For instance, predictive policing algorithms may disproportionately target marginalized communities, exacerbating existing biases and perpetuating systemic inequalities. Similarly, AI-driven welfare systems may inadvertently deny benefits to vulnerable individuals due to flawed data or algorithmic biases. These risks highlight the urgent need for legal frameworks that explicitly address the human rights implications of AI and ensure its deployment aligns with constitutional principles. The integration of AI into public decision-making processes presents a profound challenge to existing legal and constitutional frameworks. Addressing these challenges requires a re-evaluation of how legal systems adapt to technological innovation, ensuring that the deployment of AI is grounded in clear legal authority, transparency, and accountability. Without such a framework, the use of AI risks undermining the rule of law, eroding public trust, and infringing on fundamental rights. A settled constitutional response is therefore essential to navigate the complexities of AI while safeguarding democratic principles and human rights.

2.2. Dark patterns, manipulative design and AI regulation

Dark patterns, particularly those powered by AI, represent a growing challenge for regulatory frameworks, as they exploit user vulnerabilities through subliminal and manipulative design.

The rise of AI-powered dark patterns has introduced a new dimension to the challenges of regulating digital design. Dark patterns, defined as user interface designs that manipulate users into making decisions they might not otherwise make, have evolved from simple visual tricks to sophisticated, AI-driven systems that exploit individual vulnerabilities. These patterns are not always overtly deceptive but are nonetheless effective in influencing behaviour, often in ways that are harmful or exploitative. The integration of AI into these designs has amplified their impact, making them more personalised and harder to detect, while also complicating regulatory efforts. This issue becomes even more pronounced in decentralized and autonomous services, where the absence of a central authority makes enforcement of consumer protection measures more challenging. For instance, platforms like *pump.fun*, is recently banned in the UK.

The AI Act and the forthcoming Digital Fairness Act represent attempts to address these challenges. Article 5(1)(a) and (b) of the AI Act, for instance, prohibit the use of AI systems that deploy subliminal techniques or manipulative designs to distort user behaviour. However, these

prohibitions are not without limitations. The thresholds for enforcement are high, requiring proof that the manipulation is both intentional and results in significant harm. This creates a regulatory gap where many manipulative practices, particularly those that are subtle or context-dependent, may escape scrutiny. For example, AI systems that use inaudible sounds or non-obvious colour schemes to influence user behaviour may not meet the threshold for prohibition unless they cause demonstrable harm. This raises questions about the effectiveness of current regulatory frameworks in addressing the nuanced and evolving nature of dark patterns.

A key issue is the distinction between static user interface dark patterns and algorithmic dark patterns. Static dark patterns, such as misleading cookie banners or hidden unsubscribe buttons, are relatively straightforward to identify and regulate. Algorithmic dark patterns, on the other hand, are dynamic and adaptive, leveraging user data to tailor manipulative strategies to individual behaviours and vulnerabilities. For instance, an AI system might learn that a user with dyslexia is more likely to click on certain visual cues and then design an interface to exploit this vulnerability. This level of personalization makes algorithmic dark patterns particularly insidious, as they are not only harder to detect but also more effective in achieving their manipulative goals.

The regulatory response to these challenges has been fragmented. While the AI Act and Digital Fairness Act provide a foundation, their focus on static dark patterns and high thresholds for enforcement limits their effectiveness in addressing algorithmic manipulation. Moreover, the lack of transparency in how AI systems operate complicates efforts to hold developers and deployers accountable. For example, in the context of tax declaration systems, AI might be used to nudge users toward more honest reporting. While this could serve a public interest, it also raises ethical questions about the extent to which such manipulation is justified and how it aligns with principles of autonomy and informed consent.

The vulnerability of certain groups further complicates the regulatory landscape. Article 5(1)(b) of the AI Act acknowledges the need to protect vulnerable individuals from manipulative practices, but defining and identifying vulnerability in the context of AI-driven dark patterns remains a challenge. For instance, users with cognitive impairments or limited digital literacy may be disproportionately affected by manipulative designs, yet current regulations lack the granularity to address these specific risks. This highlights the need for a more nuanced approach to regulation, one that considers the diverse ways in which AI can exploit individual vulnerabilities. This includes lowering the thresholds for enforcement, addressing the unique challenges posed by algorithmic dark patterns, and ensuring that regulatory frameworks are

equipped to protect vulnerable groups. Without such measures, the potential for AI to exploit user vulnerabilities will continue to grow, undermining trust in digital systems and eroding the ethical foundations of AI deployment.

2.3. Blockchain for AI governance

While blockchain presents its own set of regulatory challenges, its perceived inherent architecture advantages in data governance and transparency offer promising solutions for AI governance. By integrating blockchain mechanisms into the AI lifecycle, it has the potential to enhance oversight, accountability, and trust in AI systems.

Blockchain's decentralized and immutable ledger ensures that data used in AI development is securely recorded and traceable. This capability is crucial for verifying the origin and integrity of datasets, thereby enhancing transparency and trust in AI systems. Through the trace-back mechanism, blockchain can also empower copyright holders to identify the original sources of content used in AI training and operations. This capability enables precise attribution and ensures that intellectual property rights are respected throughout the AI lifecycle. By providing a verifiable audit trail, blockchain fosters accountability and discourages unauthorized use or misappropriation of creative content. In the same vein, blockchain offers a robust framework to protect personal data within AI systems. On one hand, data subjects can trace the origin of their personal data, ensuring transparency about where and how it was obtained. On the other hand, cryptographic techniques, such as zero-knowledge proofs, enable the verification of data integrity without revealing sensitive information. This approach can substantially protect the content of sensitive information, while still enabling its use for AI development.

Furthermore, blockchain can provide decentralized governance for autonomous AI agents by establishing a transparent, accountable framework that leverages decentralized autonomous organizations (DAOs). DAOs can be created to facilitate decentralized, participatory governance of AI agents. By enabling stakeholders, including developers, regulators, ethicists, and end-users, to vote on policy changes and risk classifications, DAOs can democratise decision-making and distribute oversight responsibilities. Future research might explore models for weighted voting mechanisms and reputation systems that ensure balanced contributions from diverse stakeholder groups while maintaining rapid and effective governance processes.

Additionally, blockchain architecture can be used to valid the outputs of GenAI and AI Agents to reach a consensus. Because GenAI systems often produce inconsistent or unreliable outputs, raising concerns about trustworthiness in critical applications, blockchain can offer a

decentralized framework to address this challenge by enabling consensus-based validation across multiple GenAI models. It can first receive outputs from multiple AI agents in response to a single user query, with metadata (e.g., model version, data sources) hashed and stored on-chain. Second, a decentralized network of validators, comprising domain-specific AI agents, human experts, or hybrid arbitrators, evaluates responses against predefined metrics such as factual accuracy, logical coherence, and alignment with ethical guidelines. Validators' inputs are weighted by on-chain reputation scores, which reflect their historical performance, incentivizing rigorous assessments. Finally, smart contracts aggregate these evaluations, applying consensus algorithms (e.g., Byzantine) to select the most trustworthy output. This process not only identifies high-quality responses but also dynamically updates model reputations, creating a self-improving ecosystem where reliable agents gain influence over time.

The core assumption is that while individual models and AI agents may generate flawed responses, aggregating and comparing outputs from diverse agents, each trained on distinct data or optimised for specific tasks, increases the likelihood of surfacing accurate, ethical, and contextually appropriate answers. Blockchain's immutable ledger ensures transparency in this process, recording all model outputs, validation criteria, and stakeholder votes to create an auditable trail for accountability.

2.4. AI Regulation Challenges from a Global Perspective

Highly contrasting approaches in AI regulation expose risks and benefits. The EU may have acted too early to regulate AI, whereas China takes a fragmented approach. Given the sensitive nature of AI for national interests, regulation is likely to be weaponized.

2.4.1. AI regulation in the EU

The European Union's AI Act represents one of the first comprehensive attempts to regulate AI on a principle-based framework, drawing heavily on guidelines from the OECD. While the Act is a significant step forward, its implementation faces several challenges. One of the most notable issues is the lack of clarity in its legal drafting. Many provisions are vague or overly broad, leading to uncertainty for developers and end-users alike. For example, Article 5 of the AI Act prohibits certain high-risk AI applications, such as lie detectors used by immigration authorities. However, such technologies are not yet widely deployed, raising questions about the practicality and relevance of these prohibitions.

Another challenge is the horizontal nature of the AI Act, which creates overlaps and contradictions with existing sector-specific laws, particularly in areas like finance and

healthcare. This legal uncertainty is exacerbated by the fact that multiple regulators are responsible for enforcing the Act, leading to potential conflicts and inefficiencies. For instance, while the AI Act aims to protect fundamental rights, its vague provisions and lack of clear enforcement mechanisms may undermine its effectiveness. Despite these challenges, the AI Act provides a foundation for future regulatory efforts. Its emphasis on involving technical experts and building a governance system is a positive step. However, the success of the Act will depend on its ability to adapt to the rapid pace of technological innovation and address the gaps in its current framework.

2.4.2. AI regulation in China

In contrast to the EU's centralized approach, China's AI regulatory landscape is highly fragmented. Multiple administrative bodies oversee AI development and deployment, creating a complex and often contradictory regulatory environment. This fragmentation increases compliance costs for companies and hinders the development of a unified regulatory framework. For example, while the Chinese government has been actively discussing AI legislation for the past two years, no final decision has been reached, leaving companies to navigate a patchwork of local and national regulations.

One of the key challenges in China is the lack of transparency in AI systems. Companies are often reluctant to disclose their data practices or algorithmic methodologies due to concerns about intellectual property and commercial secrets. This lack of transparency not only undermines public trust but also complicates efforts to regulate AI effectively. Additionally, the rapid pace of AI innovation in China, driven by significant venture capital investment, has outpaced the ability of regulators to keep up, creating a regulatory gap that leaves consumers and businesses vulnerable. Despite these challenges, China's focus on AI development presents opportunities for global collaboration. By aligning its regulatory efforts with international standards, China will play a key role in shaping the future of AI governance.

3. Next steps

The decentralized economy and AI governance present complicated, evolving regulatory challenges that require careful balancing between innovation and control. While decentralized technologies promise greater autonomy and efficiency, they also introduce risks related to trust, fragmentation, and enforcement. Similarly, AI regulation must navigate issues of transparency, accountability, and ethical considerations, with global approaches diverging significantly. As governments and regulators grapple with these challenges, interdisciplinary insights from past regulatory cycles can inform more effective, adaptable frameworks.

Under CREATE's new research theme 'Decentralization, Automation, Platforms', we advance interdisciplinary research on the regulation of emerging technologies, focusing on AI governance, decentralized systems, and digital market regulation. We will engage in research, projects and events that aim to develop AI-based interactive digital resources on GDPR empirical evidence, study the real-world impact of the EU AI Act, explore new applications of competition law and financial regulation in the decentralized economy, and continue to maintain our competition law database.

CREATE

Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy

School of Law / University of Glasgow

10 The Square

Glasgow G12 8QQ

www.create.ac.uk

2025/03 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15065455

CC BY-SA 4.0

In collaboration with:

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council